

Use of Information Sources and Services by the Students of the Government Degree College, Billawar, Kathua: A survey

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Abstract: This study investigates the usage of information sources and services by students at the Govt. Degree College, Billawar. A structured questionnaire was framed to collect data. A sample size of 300 students from the college was selected randomly out of which 250 students were given complete information regarding the survey. Questionnaires were distributed to the students personally by hand in order to get the maximum responses. The collected data was organized and interpreted by using a simple statistical method.

Keywords: Library Resources, Information Sources, Information Services, College Library.

1. INTRODUCTION

The library is considered the backbone of every educational institution. It cannot function properly if its library is not well maintained. The library in the college is used by different user categories such as students, teaching and non-teaching staff to fulfill their information needs. Librarian properly implements the information programs among the users so that they could enhance their learning skills and ability. The main function of the library is to collect, store and maintain documents and resources in the library and provide them to the users for fulfilling their information needs. With the advancement of ICT, the process of information generation and its use among users has changed and finding correct and essential information is more important than finding information.

The library of Govt. Degree College, Billawar was established in 2005 with the establishment of the college. Now the college offers courses on various disciplines to the students and with this library collection has increased by about 13,000. The collection of the library is in print form and most of the collection is subject-specific. The library has generated a database of its all resources for easy and prompt retrieval of information resources. Moreover, the library has obtained subscriptions from various online learning platforms for quenching the academic thirst of its user clientele. The library provides services of various in-house operations to faculty and students of the institution such as circulation, reference services, and other allied processes.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the purpose of the users to visit the library.
2. To examine the frequency of usage of library by the users.
3. To find the information sources available in the library.
4. To examine the sources consulted by the users during library visit.

Scope and limitation

The scope of the present study is limited to the usage of information sources and services by the students of Govt. Degree College, Billawar, Kathua. The study is limited to 300 students. Out of 300 students, 250 have responded and 50 have not responded.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

There are various numbers of techniques and tools which are available for researchers to collect data. These are as questionnaire methods, observation method, interview method, pilot study etc.

This study is based on the survey method (Questionnaire method). A well-structured questionnaire is designed to collect data from the students of the Govt. Degree College, Billawar, Kathua. Keeping in view the objectives of the study. The collected data is tabulated and systematically analyzed by using simple statistical methods.

Responses from the students

Category	No. of questionnaire distributed	No. of questionnaire received back	%age of questionnaire received back
Student	300	250	83.33%
Total	300	250	83.33%

The respondents were asked about the use of college library of the Government Degree College, Billawar. Their responses are showed in the below table (table1)

Table 1: Use of College Library

S. No	Sources	No. of Responses	%age of Responses
1.	Yes	240	96%
2.	No	10	4%
Total		250	100

Table 1 is indicated that about (240) 96% of users use college library and (10) 4% of users does not use library. This indicated that the maximum users use the library.

The respondents were asked about the time spent in the library of Government Degree College, Billawar. Their responses are indicated in the table 2.

Table 2: Time Spent by the Users in the Library

S. No	Sources	No. of Responses	%age of Responses
1.	Less than one Hour	215	86%
2.	One Hour	20	8%
3.	Two Hour	10	4%
4.	More than Two Hour	5	2%
	Total	250	100

With respect to time spent in the library, it is indicated from table 2 that about (215) 86% of users spent less than one hour in the library, (20) 8% of users spent only one hour in the library, (10) 4% of users spent two hour, (5) 2% of users spent more than two hour in the library. This clearly shows that the maximum users spent less than one Hour in the library.

The respondents were asked about the frequency of use in the library of the Government Degree College Billawar. Their responses are showed in the below table (Table 3)

Table 3: Frequency of Use

S. No	Sources	No. of Responses	%age of Responses
1.	Daily	220	88%
2.	Weekly	15	6%
3.	Fortnightly	10	4%
4	Monthly	5	2%
	Total	250	100

Table 3 indicated that about (220) 88% of users use their frequency is Daily, (15) 6% of users use their frequency is Weekly, about (10) 4% of users use their frequency is Fortnightly, while (5) 2% of users use their frequency is Monthly. The table clearly shows that the maximum frequency of users to use library is Daily.

The respondents were asked about the purpose of visit the library of the Government Degree College Billawar. Their response is showed in the below Table (Table4).

Table 4: Purpose Visit in the Library

S. No	Sources	No. of Responses	%age of Responses
1.	To consult various books	25	10%
2.	To get and read books	150	60%
3.	To read newspaper	50	20%
4.	To read magazines	25	10%
	Total	250	100

The above table (Table 4) indicated that about (25) 10% of users consult various books, (150) 60% of users get and read books, (50) 20% of users read newspaper and (25) 10% users read magazines. This shows that the maximum users get and read books.

The respondents were asked about the sources consulted by them in the library of the Government Degree College Billawar. Their responses are showed the below table (Table 5)

Table 5: Sources Consulted by Users in the Library

S. No	Sources	No. of Responses	%age of Responses
1.	Text Books	150	60%
2.	General Books	30	12%
3.	Newspaper	50	20%
4.	Magazines	20	8%
	Total	250	100

As per above table, it is indicated that about (150) 60% of users consult Text Books, (30) 12% of users consult General Books, (50) 20% of users consult Newspaper while (20) 8% of users consult Magazines. The table shows that, maximum users consult Text Books in the library.

The respondents were asked about the availability of reading room facilities in the library of the Government Degree College, Billawar. Their responses are showed in the below table (Table 6)

Table 6: Availability of Reading Room Facility in the Library

S. No.	Sources	No. of Responses	%age of Responses
1.	Adequate	110	44%
2.	Inadequate	140	56%
Total		250	100

With respect to the availability of reading room facilities in the library, it is indicated that about (110) 44% of users say that the library provide adequate reading room facilities while (140) 56% of users say that library provide inadequate reading room facilities in the library of the Government Degree College, Billawar. This shows that maximum users find inadequate reading room facilities in the library of the Government Degree College, Billawar.

The respondents were asked about their satisfaction with the circulation services in the library of the Government Degree College, Billawar. Their responses are showed in the below table (Table7)

Table 7: Satisfaction with Circulation Services

S. No	Sources	No. of Responses	%age of Responses
1.	Yes	120	48%
2.	No	130	52%
	Total	250	100

The above table is indicated that about (120) 48% of users satisfied and (130) 52% of users satisfied with the circulation services in the library of the Government Degree College, Billawar. This shows that maximum users are not satisfied with the circulation services of the library.

The respondents were asked about the attitudes of the library staff towards the users of the Government Degree College, Billawar. Their responses are indicated in Table 8

Table 8: Attitude of Library Staff towards the Users

S. No	Sources	No. of Responses	%age of Responses
1.	Always ready to help	100	40%
2.	Generally Helpful	90	36%
3.	Not very helpful	25	10%
4.	No opinion	35	14%
	Total	250	100

The above table is indicated that about (100) 40% of users say that the library staff is always ready to help, (90) 36% of users say that the library staff is generally helpful, about (25) 10% of users says that the library staff is not very helpful, while (35) 14% of users give no opinion about the attitude of the staff towards users. This shows that the maximum users say that the library staff is always ready to help the users of the Government Degree College Billawar.

3. FINDINGS

On the basis of analysis of the survey, the following findings can be arrived which are as under:

- It is observed that (240) 96% users of the college use library while (10) 4% users do not use college library as mentioned from table 1.
- About (215) 86% users of the college spent less than one hour while only (5) 2% users spent more than 2 hours in the library as mentioned from table 2.
- The frequency of users visits the library on Daily basis is maximum which is (220) 88% while the frequency of users visit the library on monthly basis is minimum which is (5) 2%. This clearly mention from table 3.
- Table 4 clearly indicates that about (150) 60% users visit the library for the purpose of getting and reading the books while (25) 10% users visit the library for consulting various books and reading magazines.
- Although the library has rich collection of sources but the sources which is consulted most by the users (150) 60% is text books while only (20) 8% users consult magazines.
- Table 6 shows that for (110) 44% users, the availability of reading room facilities are adequate while (140) 56% users give their responses inadequate towards the reading room facilities in the library
- Based on the responses of users, it is seen that (120) 48% users satisfy with the circulation services of the library while (130) 52% users have not satisfied with the circulation services of the library.
- Based on the responses of users regarding the attitude of library staff towards users, it is seen that (100) 40% users say that library staff is always helpful while (35) 14% users give no opinion as indicated from table 8.

4. SUGGESTIONS

1. Library orientation programs should be conducted for fresh students.
2. Library awareness programs should be conducted time to time in the library.
3. Books having more demand in the library should have multiple copies in the library.
4. Wi-fi connectivity should be provided in the library.
5. Latest editions of books should be purchased every year for the benefits of teachers and students.
6. The location of the library should be at the centre of the college.

7. The library staff should update their skills by taking participation in various programs conducted by various library organizations.
8. The number of reading rooms with comfortable chairs and tables should be increased.
9. Library should be properly cleaned.
10. Proper lightening system, windows for natural light, infrastructure should be there in the library.
11. More than two books should be issued to the users at a time.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Library provides various types of resources and services to its users. Its success depends upon the fulfillment of the information needs of the users. The college library has a rich collection of various information resources and is mostly present in print form. The library should conduct orientation programs for its users to acquaint them with various in-house operations of the library for maximum utilization of information resources. The library staff should update themselves with new skills and do their best to fulfill the requirement of their users. The librarian should make every possible effort to offer library services in the best possible way and make the college library a temple of learning in the true sense.

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